

Article

PROMOTING MUSICAL LEARNING IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY: PARENTS' PERSPECTIVES

Appendix 1

Table I - Objectives and questions to ask Parents of children with CP

Objectives	Questions
Objective1: To introduce, 'break the ice' and get to know the image that Parents have of their children, their development, daily life at home and their characteristics	p1. I'd like you to start by telling us a bit about your child. What are his/her defining characteristics?
Objective2: Identify what interests the child and what they like to do, to better characterise the child taking part in the study	p2. What activities does he/she like to do? What are your child's interests? What are your child's strengths? Could you tell me?
Objective3: To check whether Parents are aware of how their child assimilates knowledge, whether they think they learn and how they learn, as well as to record Parents' representations of their children's learning and contribute to characterising the children	p3. How does your child access knowledge? How do they most like to learn, study texts, videos, images, etc?
Objective4: Identify what Parents perceive as necessary for their child to learn better (what Parents miss to enhance their child's learning)	p4. What could facilitate your child's learning at school/home and access to school or other content?
Objective5: Check whether Parents are aware of Technologies: Digital Technologies (DT) and Assistive Technology (AT) (even those that are digitally based), and how and how regularly they use them (frequency of use, alone, with Parents, with siblings, only at school, etc.)	p5. Does your child use DT/AT daily? If so, which ones? How? In what contexts?
Objective6: Identify what kind of artistic activities children with CP attend, in what contexts, where, how and with whom	p6. Does your child have access to artistic and musical activities? Which ones? Where? How? With whom?
Objective7: To check whether Parents are aware of the type of adaptations that are possible so that their child can have access to artistic/musical activities	p7. In your opinion, what kind of adaptations can facilitate the process of including your child in artistic/musical activities?
Objective8: Open questions for any issues that Parents feel are relevant to raise	p8. Are there any other aspects that you think are important to mention?

Table II . Some examples of answers and their discussion

OBJECTIVES (see Table 1)	EXAMPLES OF ANSWERS	DISCUSSION
Objective1	<i>My son is a very lively child, very clever. He has his naughtiness and even with his limitations, he's very playful (P2); My daughter is a girl who doesn't speak, doesn't walk on her own, but is starting to get around on her own with a walker (P1); My daughter is a good-natured, happy girl, above all, stubborn and does only what she likes (P3); My son is a calm child, sometimes a little nervous (P9); My son is a special child, although on the surface he's a completely normal child (P11); My son is dependent on adult support. He needs an adult to help him eat, clean himself and get around (P7); She currently moves around in a wheelchair. She doesn't walk and can't walk, but ... in terms of cognition, she's doing very well (P8); When my daughter was little, she didn't have any movement in her arms or legs. But with a lot of therapy, really a lot of therapy, she's managed to have a bit more strength, especially in her arms rather than her legs, which she can move (P8); You can now understand very well what my daughter means. It's all thanks to the work done by the speech therapist, occupational therapist and physiotherapist who have been with her since she was little (P12); She's a child who needs a lot of diversified strategies and a lot of motivation for her day-to-day learning (P1); It's thanks to the therapies that CPA provides that my daughter has been able to evolve and become the child she is now (P14).</i>	The information compiled and related to this objective (see Table 1) gives us the impression that the Parents know the children well (see Table 2). They know how they behave, how they develop, how they learn, and what's more, they inform us about their limitations, their setbacks, therapies and medication. They also give us an insight into some of the problems they have experienced in their development as a family with their children with CP.
Objective2	<i>My daughter loves to sing, sometimes she doesn't understand anything, but she's always humming the songs she hears (P12): With all his difficulties, he loves to play ball. Playing, he likes playing with kitchens. Anything that involves vegetables, pots and pans and all that sort of thing (P6); He likes technology, maths and he also likes artistic things. He likes new things, things that excite him (P10).</i>	By compiling this information, we were able to find out what they like to do, what they like to play with, how they play and what kind of games they play. Demonstrating that children with CP are just like all other children, with varied interests, they play and develop with the activities and possibilities available to them.
Objective3	<i>He's a quick learner, despite the spasms and all those things he has, he's a quick learner (P6); Even if they're songs in English, she listens to the songs and gets the hang of it, she doesn't say the words of the song, but she gets there... she gets there. My daughter understands and repeats what she learns... (P12); My daughter's strongest point is that she never gives up. Even if she doesn't succeed, she tries and even if it takes her two or three times, she never gives up until she succeeds and never gets discouraged. Never (P12).</i>	The information compiled suggests that parents are aware of how their child acquires knowledge, perceiving different strategies such as developing play, telling stories or listening to songs. They include processes that use skills such as listening, memorisation and repetition to develop the assimilation and learning of content and strategies that facilitate their learning process.
Objective4	<i>That's the big problem we have. There aren't enough people with the specific knowledge to know how to work with our children and that's a shame because when my son was little, he was never motivated to learn and now that he's older it's much more difficult (P7); If teachers explained the subject in a more accessible way, it would help a lot. Maybe the lessons would be more dynamic, with more drawings, more playful activities, I don't know... something like that (P14); if there is no support or continuity in the activities, any child ends up forgetting how to do them and ends up standing still, without developing. Unfortunately, that's what happened to my son (P7); I think that inclusion, real inclusion, hasn't happened yet. Inclusion in practice still doesn't happen (P5); He doesn't like being excluded. My son can't speak, but his problem isn't cognitive, so</i>	From the responses compiled, we can see that parents have their strategies for captivating their children's attention daily. The children require constant support from their parents to be able to carry out activities. We also observed that they consider teachers to have doubts and lack preparation on how to work with children with CP and need support (technological) and support (people) in the classroom. As

	<i>he understands everything that happens around him and hates it when he's excluded (P10); What we should improve so that my daughter is more included is accessibility, we should start there... firstly at the school she's at, the entrance to the school isn't easy, it's not accessible (long silence)... we need to think about more inclusion... (P13).</i>	well as accessibility and the need to promote school inclusion.
Objective 5	My son uses the computer, he uses the PC Eye Mini and GRID3, which is a programme on the computer, with the help of the PC Eye Mini he does everything (P2); My son uses digital technologies and AT in his day-to-day life. We have GRID3, the computer, and the PC Eye Mini offered by Telecom (P6); My son used SmartNAVE, which was for moving his head, but it was much more difficult. It didn't work (P9); Having a computer at school would make my granddaughter's learning much easier. She could do her homework much more easily (P4); It would make it much easier for my son to learn at school, something the special education teacher is trying to arrange. It would be an adapted tablet. So that he can speak without speaking (P11).	The answers compiled for this objective suggest that parents know, use, or would like to use, Technology, DT, and AT even more. Parents value and consider that Technology has facilitated children's access to school content, for some it is the only form of access. In this context, they consider that CRTICs have collaborated positively with the prescription of APs as well as with the monitoring and facilitation of each of the APs that their children use.
Objective6	<i>My son doesn't have access to artistic and musical activities (P2); I tried to enrol my daughter in music. But they said they didn't have the necessary number of 'disabled pupils' to be able to create an exclusive course for them and thus form a class (P3); My son likes music, he could be playing, for example, the xylophone, I have one and he likes to play it. I'd like my son to learn music. But he doesn't have access to artistic musical activities (P11); We shouldn't close the doors to children who are different, even in higher education or at the conservatoire, everyone has the right to music and so they should have opportunities (P12); What they offered at the JOBRA Conservatoire was music therapy, not music teaching. I realise that they are different things (P3); I think that music therapy helps a lot in the development of our children. In Brazil, I worked with children with EN for 15 years and the children who work with music therapy develop much better than other children (P5).</i>	Parents emphasise in their answers that their children enjoy music, singing, dancing and participating, but in many cases they don't have access to musical activities or affordable musical instruments, even though they think these activities would be an asset for the children. They also mention the music therapy support that is available in some schools - even though music therapy is not recognised in Portugal.
Objective7	<i>It would be good if there was the possibility of having ADMI that my son could play, for example, on the computer, rather than by hand (he doesn't have much manual dexterity). Software that could provide access to different musical instruments that my son could choose, through the software on the computer and play, would be so good if that were possible (P2); What I think is that at school they are limiting the children and not providing differentiated solutions. For example, at school, they require all pupils to play the flute, and my son can't play the flute. There should be alternative musical instruments (P10); Music teaching would have better results with children with CP if, perhaps, the musical instruments were adapted (P14).</i>	We believe that the Parents are aware that adaptations would be necessary for their children to have access to artistic and musical activities. They believe that music teaching could have better results if the musical instruments were adapted to the needs of children with CP, whether or not they used AT, because the most important thing for some of them is to encourage the child's development through music.
Objective8	<i>I think we need to get out of our comfort zone, we need to fight for public policies in favour of our children, in favour of children with CP (P5); It's difficult to continue with the therapies, it's a struggle to make ends meet, for example, the minimum cost of a therapy is 20 euros an hour and my daughter has to be in therapies for at least three hours a week, 60 euros in total, I can't make ends meet (P9); All the donations they gave to my daughter were only for physiotherapy and what I spent on diesel, car expenses, tolls, time off work to go with her, nobody considers. I know it's my responsibility. But it's hard, I can't do it, I'm tired... (P13).</i>	The information compiled here talks specifically about the needs that parents have to cope with day-to-day life with their children. The time they spend with their children to take them to therapies and the lack of financial resources mean that parents always feel hard done by and, in a way, excluded from life in society. There is an urgent need for the state to develop more supportive public policies to facilitate the development of children in favour of inclusion.

